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Partial shading of one solar cell in a photovoltaic module with 3-terminal cell interconnection

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ABSTRACT

We examine the electrical and thermal characteristics of a photovoltaic module with three-terminal cell interconnection when partially shading a solar cell by experimentally verified modeling. For the interconnection of multi junction and tandem solar cells a two- (2T), three- (3T), and four-terminal (4T) cell architecture is conceivable. The 3T architecture featuring a combination of parallel and series interconnection combines the advantageous of 2T and 4T cells without their drawbacks. We build a photovoltaic (PV) module with silicon solar cells in a 3T tandem solar cell interconnection configuration (3TTSC PV module) to emulate a solar module with 20 3TTSC. To the best of our knowledge, no 3TTSC PV module with more than five solar cells has been shown in previous studies. We measure the effect of partially shading a 3TTSC in this module and develop an electrical simulation to model our experimental results. In the simulations we determine the dissipated power in the top and bottom cells due to the current mismatch caused by partial shading. Our results reveal that the shaded top and bottom cell as well as the adjacent top cell dissipate power when a single 3TTSC is shaded. The two top cells share the dissipated power. Our simulated power dissipation correlates with temperature measurements of the 3TTSC PV module in a steady-state sun simulator. Therefore, in a 3TTSC PV module the temperature of a shaded cell is lower than in a module with 2T configuration. This is an advantage of PV modules with 3T tandem solar cells in terms of reliability and long-term stability.

1. Introduction

Silicon (Si) based tandem solar cells potentially increase the cell efficiency beyond the theoretical limit of single junction Si solar cells. Today, record cell efficiencies of 29.1 % for perovskite/Si and 32.8 % for GaAs/Si have been reported for tandem solar cells [11, 6]. For the interconnection of these tandem solar cells into a photovoltaic (PV) module a two- (2T), three- (3T), and four-terminal (4T) cell architecture is conceivable [13, 21]. The 2T series connection requires current matched top (TC) and bottom cells (BC). Thus, 2T tandem solar cells (2TTSC) are optimized for a certain spectrum, which constrains the combinations of materials with different band gaps. Further it reduces their annual yield at outdoor operation due to naturally varying spectra [17]. 4T tandem solar cells (4TTSC) are advantageous in terms of combining materials with different band gaps and spectral variations since TC and BC operate independently. However, 4TTSC have a higher manufacturing complexity and are potentially more expensive since they require transparent, laterally conductive layers between the TC and BC and need additional wiring for the connection to an external circuit [15]. A 3T tandem solar cell (3TTSC) architecture combines the simpler processing of a monolithic 2TTSC with the performance advantage of a 4TTSC [13, 17, 20, 16]. Connecting 3T tandem solar cells in a PV module (denoted as 3TTSC PV module in this work) was first proposed by

Gee [5]. One drawback of the interconnection is that in total the power of one TC and one BC is lost in a string, which is negligible for long cell strings [5, 22].

Although there are many theoretical studies dealing with the advantages of interconnecting tandem solar cells with 3T architecture [13, 17, 5], only a few report on experimental results for this interconnection technique [22]. Due to the higher power of tandem solar cells, long-term reliability issues as they may occur due to current mismatch caused by partial shading of the module are important. Qian et al. [12] showed that partial shading results in theoretical cell temperatures of 207°C for 2TTSC and 137°C for 4TTSC, which is above the temperature limit of standard solar modules and perovskite solar cells. However, investigations of modules with 3T tandem solar cells are missing, though these are particularly interesting due to the parallel/series interconnection and their advantageous over modules with 2TTSC and 4TTSC.

In this study, we build a PV module with a parallel/series connection of 20 3TTSC, emulating two substrings connected to a bypass diode as in a typical conventional 60-cell Si module. To the best of our knowledge, no 3TTSC PV module with more than five solar cells has been shown in previous studies. We measure and simulate the module power for four interconnection scenarios of this module. Furthermore, we examine the effect of partially shading one solar cell in the 3TTSC PV module in accordance to the IEC 61215-2 MQT09 standard (hot spot endurance test) [8].

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Figure 1: (a) Photo and (b) circuit diagram of the solar module with full and halved Si cells emulating a 3TTSC PV module. In (b) the 20 3T tandem solar cells (3TTSC) are labeled from 1 through 20. Each 3TTSC consists of an associated top cell (TC) and bottom cell (BC) as indicated for 3TTSC 1, 5, and 20. Switch S1 enables to connect or disconnect TC 1. Switch S2 either connects (position A) or disconnects (position B) BC 20.

2. Methodology and Experiments

2.1. Measuring the solar cell $I(V)$ parameters

We measure the illuminated, dark, and $I_{SC}-V_{OC}$ current-voltage ($I(V)$) characteristics of 100 industrial passivated emitter and rear c-Si solar cells (PERC) employing a LOANA measurement system [19]. Each PERC cell has dimensions of (156.75×156.75) mm and features five busbars at the front and rear side. We model the $I(V)$ data with the double diode model using SCAN [7]. Furthermore, we measure the reverse $I(V)$ characteristics of 6 PERC cells with a Neonsee Solar Cell Analysis Systems [10]. This system allows for $I(V)$ measurements down to -40 V with a current limit of -15 A.

2.2. Building a 3TTSC PV module

We build a 3TTSC PV module using 40 PERC cells to emulate a parallel/series interconnection of 20 3T tandem solar cells. Figure 1 (a) shows a photo of the 3TTSC PV module. Each 3TTSC consists of two sub-cells, i.e. a top cell (TC) and a bottom cell (BC). The 20 full-sized (156.75×156.75) mm² PERC cells represent the bottom cells. We cut the remaining 20 PERC cells into half-cells with a dimension of (156.75×78.38) mm² and connect two half-cells in series. These two half-cells represent one top cell. Thus, the TC have twice the voltage and half the current of the BC in our 3TTSC PV module. This allows an optimal voltage matching of the sub-cells [17, 5]. For the sub-cell interconnection we solder SnPbAg coated copper ribbon with dimensions of (1.3×0.2) mm² onto the cells. The interconnection of the 3T tandem solar cells within the string we realize with SnPbAg coated copper cell interconnection ribbons (CIR) with dimensions of (6×0.3) mm². For the PV module we laminate the 3TTSC between two polymer sheets of ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA), with a low-iron glass on the front and a transparent polymer backsheets on the rear side. We locally open the backsheets and the rear EVA layer to contact the CIR, which allows to sense the voltage of the individual top and bottom cells.

Figure 1 (b) shows a circuit diagram of the cell intercon-

nection for our 3TTSC PV module. The larger single diodes indicate the BCs from the full-sized PERC cells and the two smaller in series connected diodes indicate the two halved PERC cells to emulate the TCs. These 20 top and bottom cells emulate 20 two-junction 3TTSC. The 3TTSC are labeled from 1 to 20 in Fig. 1 (b). Each label of a 3TTSC also identifies the associated pair of top and bottom cells, e.g. 3TTSC 1 consists of TC 1 and BC 1. For the 3TTSC 2 through 19 one top cell is always connected in parallel to two in series connected bottom cells. At the ends of the string, this repetitive sequence is interrupted because no further 3TTSC follow.

Figure 1 (b) indicates two switches labeled with S1 and S2 that allow to modify the 3TTSC interconnection at the string ends. S1 enables to either connect or disconnect the first top cell - TC 1. When S1 is open TC 1 is disconnected and when S1 is closed TC 1 is connected to a common port with TC 2. Hence, in case S1 is closed TC 1 and TC 2 are connected in parallel. S2 allows to connect or disconnect the last bottom cell - BC 20. When S2 is in position A, BC 20 is connected in series with all previous bottom cells. When S2 is in position B, BC 20 is disconnected and in open circuit.

2.3. $I(V)$ measurements of the 3TTSC PV module with a shaded cell

For the $I(V)$ measurement of the PV module under standard testing conditions (STC) we employ a HALM flasher system. We measure the module's $I(V)$ characteristics for various combinations of switch S1 and S2, i.e. S1 is either opened or closed and S2 is either in position A or in position B.

Subsequently, we measure the individual sub-cell voltages within the flasher system for BC 3 through BC 5 as well as TC 3 through TC 5 by contacting the CIR of each sub-cell at the locally opened rear side of the module. For the voltage measurement we connect a resistor between the module's terminals to operate the module at the maximum power point (MPP). Switch S1 is closed and switch S2 is in position B for all voltage measurements. We equally shade BC 4 and TC 4 simultaneously by a shading fraction $S = \{0, 0.2, \dots, 1\}$

Figure 2: Photo of the 3TTSC PV module in the steady-state sun simulator. In the photo 3TTSC 4, i.e. the associated top (TC 4) and bottom cell (BC 4) are shaded.

and measure for each shading variation the voltage of BC 3, BC 4, and BC 5 as well as TC 3, TC 4, and TC 5 under STC.

2.4. Shading one 3T tandem solar cell of the 3TTSC PV module in the steady-state sun simulator

Figure 2 shows a photo of the 3TTSC PV module in the steady-state sun simulator we employ for the solar cell shading experiment. The halogen reflector lamps of the sun simulator illuminate the 3TTSC PV module with an average irradiance intensity of 925 W m^{-2} . The illumination homogeneity is 3.5 % measured with an UniformSun module [9]. The solar panel is mounted horizontally to the ground. A transparent temperature controlled plate between the module and the light source creates an artificial cool sky with a temperature of $23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. An air condition maintains an ambient temperature of $22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. During the test we monitor the irradiance in the module plane with two thermopile pyranometers.

For the whole illumination experiment the 3TTSC PV module is in short circuit as proposed by the IEC 61215 MQT09 standard [8]. Further, switch S1 is closed and switch S2 is in position B for all experiments in the steady-state sun simulator. Within the steady-state sun simulator we shade a single 3T tandem solar cell, i.e. we simultaneously shade a pair of associated top and bottom cells with a shading fraction $S = \{0, 0.2, \dots, 1\}$ to emulate the shading of one 3TTSC. Figure 2 shows the shading of 3TTSC 4 by simultaneously shading TC 4 and BC 4 with a black cardboard. The shading creates a current mismatch within the 3TTSC PV module resulting in a power dissipation in the mismatched cells. During the test we measure the temperature of the shaded and the adjacent 3TTSC with a calibrated infrared camera [4]. For each 3TTSC we start with the lowest shading fraction of $S = 0.2$ and increase the shading fraction every 10 min up to the maximum shading fraction of $S = 1$.

2.5. Electrical modeling of the 3TTSC PV module

For the electrical modeling of the 3TTSC PV module we employ the double diode model combined with a breakdown model [14, 1]. The interconnection of the individual

Figure 3: $I(V)$ characteristics of the 3TTSC PV module for varying combinations of switch S1 and S2, i.e. the first top cell TC 1 and the last bottom cell BC 20 is either connected or disconnected to the circuit. [Use Adobe Acrobat Reader to view animated plot.]

top and bottom cells is in accordance with the circuit diagram in Fig. 1 (b). We consider equal $I(V)$ parameters for all solar cells. As initial model parameters for the double diode model we use the average $I(V)$ parameters from the solar cell measurements of the 100 PERC cells. For the breakdown model we use the average parameters from the reverse $I(V)$ measurements of the 6 PERC cells. Starting with this initial parameters, we fit our model to the four module $I(V)$ measurements for the different switch positions of S1 and S2. In our fitting procedure the short circuit current density J_{SC} , dark saturation current density of the first J_{01} and second diode J_{02} , the series resistance R_S and the parallel resistance R_P are free fit parameters.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Modeling the 3TTSC PV module

Figure 3 shows our measurement and modeling results. The symbols indicate the measurement data and the lines our simulation results. Despite the different individual cell parameters and the parallel/series connection of the 20 3TTSC our model allows to qualitatively re-model the $I(V)$ characteristics of the 3TTSC PV module for the various switch combinations, which is sufficient for the purpose of this work.

Table 1 summarizes the most important parameters from the $I(V)$ measurements of the 3TTSC PV module for the four positions of switch S1 and S2. In Table 1 I_{SC} is the short circuit current, V_{OC} the open circuit voltage, P_{MPP} the power output of the module at MPP, with the corresponding current I_{MPP} and voltage V_{MPP} at this operating point.

The circuit diagram in Fig. 1 (b) indicates that there is a

Table 1

$I(V)$ parameters of the 3TTSC PV module for the four cases with different positions for switches S1 and S2. In the second column, 1 indicates that S1 is closed and 0 indicates that S1 is open.

Case	S1	S2	I_{SC} [A]	V_{OC} [V]	P_{MPP} [W]	I_{MPP} [A]	V_{MPP} [V]
I	1	A	15.5	13.40	162.4	13.9	11.69
II	0	A	14.1	13.38	158.9	13.7	11.59
III	0	B	15.3	12.74	152.3	13.7	11.11
IV	1	B	18.5	12.76	179.7	17.5	10.28

repetitive interconnection sequence, where a top cell is always connected in parallel to two bottom cells. If this sequence is continued until the string end, BC 20 is connected in series with all other bottom cells and S2 is in position A. At the beginning of the string S1 is closed and TC 1 is connected in parallel to TC 2.

Case I - S1 closed and S2 in position A: In this case the module has a maximum power output of 162.4 W. In terms of string-end losses, for this interconnection the 3TTSC PV module has the highest module power if the module has less than six 3TTSC. Here we refer to the study of Schulte-Huxel et al. [18] for further details on the analysis of the string-end losses of modules with 3TTSC interconnection. However, for our module with 20 3TTSC, TC 20 and BC 20 have to deliver a higher current than the remaining cells in the string due to the missing parallel connection at the string end. Thus, in this case these cells limit the string current and become reverse biased when decreasing the voltage below the module's MPP voltage, which is visible in the bending of the curve in Fig. 3. Reducing the module's voltage to 0 V, the module operates in short circuit as it is required for the IEC 61215 MQT09 test and a significant amount of power is dissipated in the last 3TTSC, with TC 20 dissipating 49.5 W and BC 20 dissipating 119 W. Additionally, TC 1 is pinned to half the top cell voltage since only one bottom cell is connected in parallel and the voltage matching fails. This interconnection is therefore inappropriate with regard to shading tests according to the IEC standard.

Case II - S1 open and S2 in position A: One solution to remove the pinning of TC 1 and to reduce the power dissipation in the last BC is to open switch S1. In this case, TC 2 and TC 20 as well as BC 1 and BC 20 are in reverse bias when the module operates in short circuit. Instead of two sub-cells, four sub-cells share the dissipated power. TC 2 and TC 20 dissipate 22.3 W and BC 1 and BC 20 dissipate 51.3 W. However, the module power in case II with 158.9 W is lower than in case I.

Case III - S1 open and S2 in position B: Switching S2 in position B and disconnecting BC 20 results in a similar situation as in case I, this time with BC 1 and TC 2 in reverse bias when the module operates in short circuit. For this case the module has the lowest power output of 152.3 W.

Case IV - S1 closed and S2 in position B: Closing S1 to connect TC 1 to the circuit and in parallel to TC 2 both sub-cells generate the same current as the two parallel bot-

Figure 4: Voltage of the associated top and bottom cells from 3TTSC 3, 4, and 5, when 3TTSC 4 is shaded by a varying shading fraction S . The inset illustrates the shading of 3TTSC 4 by $S = 0.4$.

tom cells. In this case, none of the sub-cells is in reverse bias and the module generates the highest power output of 179.7 W. Also regarding mismatch due to partial shading of a solar cell, this interconnection should be always preferred, as well as in terms of module performance, if there are more than five 3TTSC in the module. Note that in this work the last BC is in open circuit when S2 is in position B. Another option is to short circuit the last BC as proposed by Zehender et al. [22]. However, we consider operating the sub-cell in open circuit to be advantageous with regard to the wiring complexity of the module.

3.2. Partial shading of one 3-terminal solar cell in a PV module

We simulate the effect of shading one 3T tandem solar cell in the 3TTSC PV module to further test our electrical model. Figure 4 shows the sub-cells voltage of 3TTSC 3, 4, and 5, when 3TTSC 4 is shaded by $S = \{0, 0.2, \dots, 1\}$. For $S = 0$ the 3TTSC is fully illuminated and for $S = 1$ the 3TTSC is fully shaded. The symbols in Fig. 3 indicate the measurement and the dotted lines the simulation results with our electrical model. For all voltage measurements and simulations the module operates near the MPP, S1 is closed and S2 is in position B.

With increasing shading fraction S of 3TTSC 4 the associated top and bottom cell, i.e. TC 4 and BC 4, become reverse biased and operate at negative voltages. Additionally, TC 5 is forced into reverse bias although it is fully illuminated. TC 3 and BC 3 as well as BC 5 operate at positive bias, while their voltage increases with increasing S .

Our model fits the measurements data within the measurement uncertainty for the positive biased sub-cells. For the negative biased sub-cells, it models the data qualitatively since we have not considered injection and temperature ef-

Figure 5: Simulated dissipated power P_{diss} when (a) 3TTSC 4, representing a cell within the string and (b) 3TTSC 20, representing a cell at the string end is partially shaded. The dashed lines in (a) and (b) indicate the operating points for $S=0.4$ as in the thermal images. (c) shows a thermal image of 3TTSC 4 and 5, when 3TTSC 4 is shaded by $S=0.4$. P0, P2 and P3 indicate the maximum temperature of each sub-cell in °C with P0 for BC4, P2 for TC4, and P3 for TC5. (d) shows a thermal images of 3TTSC 19 and 20, when 3TTSC 20 is shaded by $S=0.4$. P0, P1 and P2 indicate the maximum temperature of each sub-cell in °C with P0 for BC19, P1 for TC19, and P2 for TC20.

facts in our model. All negative biased sub-cells dissipate power instead of generating it. In the worst case, the module is in short circuit, as required by the IEC 61215 MQT09 standard [8]. Then the reverse bias of TC 4, TC 5 and BC 4 is highest, resulting in the highest power dissipation. We employ our experimentally verified model to determine the

dissipated power P_{diss} in the reverse biased sub-cells, when the module operates in short circuit.

Figure 5 (a) shows the simulation results for the power dissipation in the sub-cells TC 4, TC 5, and BC 4 for a varying shading fraction applied to 3TTSC 4. For the worst-case shading 3TTSC 4 dissipates a power of 127 W. The simu-

lations reveal that the top cell with the highest power dissipation is the non-shaded sub-cell TC 5. Due to the parallel/series interconnection in the 3TTSC PV module TC 4 and TC 5 can share the dissipated power. TC 4 and TC 5 are both connected in parallel to the blocking bottom cell BC 4. These three parallel connected cells are therefore all forced into negative bias, since in total they have to carry the same current of one unshaded BC and two unshaded TC. For our 3TTSC PV module this is the case for all 3T tandem solar cells from 1 through 19. When one of these 3TTSC is shaded, besides the shaded top and bottom cell also the adjacent top cell is forced into reverse bias and dissipates power. This is usually not the case in a conventional solar module with all solar cells in series, where only the shaded solar cells dissipate the power.

The sharing of the dissipated power by the adjacent top cells works up to the string ends. For our 3TTSC PV module, this principle fails for 3TTSC 20, where no TC 21 follows. Figure 5 (b) shows the power dissipation for the sub-cells TC 19, BC 19, and TC 20, when 3TTSC 20 is shaded with a varying shading fraction S . TC 20 shows a similar power dissipation as TC 4 in Fig. 5 (a). In contrast to Fig. 5 (a), the shaded BC 20 is not dissipating power, since S2 is in position B and BC 20 in open circuit. Instead, BC 19 shows the highest power dissipation, peaking at a shading fraction of $S = 1$. With increasing shading fraction, TC 19 is blocking the current and BC 19 has to carry the whole module current. Since the module is already in short circuit, the sub-cell is in strong reverse bias and dissipates the highest power of all sub-cells in case of partial shading.

The dissipated power is converted into heat, which increases the cell temperature. Figure 5 (c) shows the thermal image of 3TTSC 4 and the adjacent 3TTSC 5, when 3TTSC 4 is 40% shaded. The marked points show the hottest positions for each sub-cell and also indicate the temperature at this positions. The hottest sub-cell is the shaded bottom cell BC 4 with a peak temperature of 113.0 °C. Considering the two top cells, the unshaded TC 5 is hotter than the shaded TC 4. The peak temperature of TC 5 is 88.8 °C while the peak temperature of TC 4 is 80.4 °C.

The measured maximum temperature for each sub-cell agrees qualitatively with the simulated power dissipation with our electrical model. At a shading fraction $S = 0.4$, BC 4 dissipates 73 W, which is the highest dissipated power of all sub-cells. The power dissipation in TC 5 is 48 W and in TC 4 it is 29 W, which explains the difference in peak temperature of 8 °C between both sub-cells.

Figure 5 (d) shows the thermal image of 3TTSC 19 and 20, when 3TTSC 20 is 40% shaded. We measure the highest temperature for sub-cell BC 19 with a peak temperature of 105.9 °C. For the two top cells we measure a higher peak temperature for the unshaded TC 19 with 76.9 °C compared to the shaded TC 20 with a peak temperature of 71.6 °C. This also correlates with our simulated power dissipation. For the shading fraction of $S = 0.4$ in Fig. 5 (c) and Fig. 5 (d), BC 19 is cooler than BC 4, which we relate to the homogeneously blocking behavior and the high breakdown voltage of 26 V of

the employed PERC cells. Although the power dissipation in BC 19 is higher than in BC 4, the power dissipation is homogeneously distributed over the whole cell area, while for the shaded BC 4 the power dissipation is mainly in the unshaded cell parts. Considering the power dissipation per illuminated cell area, BC 4 dissipates 0.50 W cm^{-2} and BC 19 0.42 W cm^{-2} , which explains the higher peak temperature for BC 4.

In fact, this also illustrates the advantage of the 3TTSC PV module, in case of partially shading homogeneously blocking solar cells with high breakdown voltages. Figure 5 (a) shows that the dissipated power in the shaded sub-cells reduces with increasing shading fraction. Thus, the power dissipation in the shaded sub-cells is high when the cell shading is small and hence, the dissipated power is distributed over a large area. When the shading fraction increases, the power dissipation in the unshaded top cell increases, which is beneficial since this top cell can always dissipate the power over the full cell area.

The lower temperatures of the sub-cells in case of partial shading reduce the risk of cell and module failures since temperature above 90 °C damage temperature-sensitive top cells, e.g. Perovskite cells [3] and temperatures above 150 °C may damage the module materials, e.g. the encapsulation polymer or the glass [2].

4. Conclusion

We build a solar module with PERC cells to emulate a PV module with 3T tandem solar cells and examine the series/parallel cell interconnection technique for 3T multi-junction solar cells. On the PV module we investigate four interconnection configurations for the string ends and the effect of partial shading of one 3TTSC.

We measure and simulate the highest module power output of 179.7 W for our 3TTSC PV module, when the first and the second top cell are connected in parallel and the last bottom cell is disconnected.

We verify an electrical model with $I(V)$ measurements on the 3TTSC PV module with different end-string interconnections and the application of various shading fractions to a solar cell in the 3TTSC PV module. We employ the electrical model to determine the dissipated power in a shaded 3T tandem solar cell and the associated sub-cells. Our findings show that the shaded bottom cell with a maximum of 89 W dissipates the highest power. Further, the shaded and the adjacent top cell share the dissipated power due to the parallel/series interconnection in the 3TTSC PV module. This reduces the total power dissipation in a single solar cell with 3T architecture.

We also test our 3TTSC PV module in a steady-state sun simulator, when a single 3T tandem solar cell is shaded by various shading fractions. Due to the current mismatch the shaded sub-cells dissipate power and heat up. The measured temperatures of the individual top and bottom cells correlate with our simulated power dissipation, i.e. the higher the dissipated power per sub-cell area the higher the sub-cell tem-

perature in the steady-state sun simulator.

Our results show, that the interconnection of 3TTSC reduces the risk of overheating in solar modules. This is an advantage of interconnecting 3T tandem solar cells compared to interconnecting 2T and 4T tandem solar cells, where only the shaded solar cells dissipate power. Thus, a 3TTSC architecture could be beneficial in terms of partial cell shading in a solar module with temperature-sensitive multi-junction solar cells like perovskites.

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